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Methods to quantify endothelial cell front-rear polarity *in vivo* and *in vitro*

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Abstract

Purpose of review

Endothelial cell (EC) front-rear (axial) polarization in response to chemokines and shear stress is fundamental for angiogenesis. This review provides an overview of the *in vitro* and *in vivo* methods that are currently available to quantify EC axial polarity.

Recent findings

Innovative methodologies and new animal models have been developed to evaluate EC axial polarity. Micropatterning, wound healing and microfluidic assays allow interrogation of signalling mechanisms *in vitro*. Mouse and zebrafish transgenic lines, in combination with advances in imaging techniques and computational tools, enable interrogation of physiological functions of EC axial polarity in vascular biology during development and in pathology *in vivo*.

Summary

We present a literature-based review of the methods available to study EC polarity. Further refinement of quantitative methods to analyse EC axial polarity using deep learning-based computational tools will generate new understanding on the aetiology of vascular malformations.

Keywords

endothelial cell; cell polarity; cell migration; image analysis.

Introduction

The vascular system is composed of a complex and hierarchically organized network that has essential functions in homeostasis and disease. The vascular system distributes oxygen, nutrients and metabolism-derived waste products through different tissues. It also provides important signalling molecules for organ development and function that are collectively known as angiocrine factors [1]. The first blood vessels form through vasculogenesis, which generates a primitive vasculature. This rudimentary network is further expanded by a process called angiogenesis [2, 3**]. In adults, vessels are normally quiescent, however, angiogenesis can be reactivated upon injury, disease, or changing metabolic demands [1, 2]. Angiogenesis is driven by endothelial cells (ECs), the cells lining the interior of blood vessels, and it involves two steps: *i)* sprouting angiogenesis, which expands pre-existing networks through proliferation, migration and anastomosis of ECs; and *ii)* vascular patterning, which converts immature networks, generated by sprouting angiogenesis, into a hierarchical/asymmetrical network of vessels, requiring vessel regression, arteriovenous differentiation and vessel specialisation [3**].

During sprouting angiogenesis, ECs migrate collectively in a cohesive way (collective cell migration – CCM) towards diverse chemotactic stimuli [4–6]. CCM is essential for sprouting and patterning of blood vessels and the development of a functional network without vascular malformations [2, 3**]. For instance, sprouting angiogenesis involves the specification of two different EC states: tip and stalk cells, which polarise and migrate through CCM [7**]. Tip cells lead newly formed vascular sprouts in response to gradients of chemokines and growth factors, such as vascular endothelial growth factor A (VEGFA). This gradient specifies directional EC migration towards avascular regions. Stalk cells migrate and proliferate behind tip cells to sustain sprout elongation [3**, 4, 6]. During vascular patterning, ECs polarise and migrate against the blood flow direction, going from low-flow/no-flow vessel segments towards high-flow segments. This specifies the regression of unproductive low-flow branches and the stabilization of high-flow branches [8–10].

In both contexts, EC migration requires front-rear (axial) polarization of cells in response to environmental factors (chemokines or flow for ECs). This axial polarisation is dictated by an asymmetric activation and distribution of many cellular components, including proteins (aPKC/Par complex, and Cdc42), lipids (PtdIns(3,4,5)P3 and PtdIns(3,4)P2), and organelles (the

microtubule organization centre (MTOC) and the Golgi apparatus) [3**]. This asymmetric distribution, in particular the Golgi apparatus, has been used to analyze EC axial polarity, *in vitro* and *in vivo* [8, 11].

In this review, we present several methodological approaches to analyse and quantify *in vitro* and *in vivo* EC axial polarity (Fig. 1).

Assays and methods to quantify endothelial cell axial polarity *in vitro*

To understand how external and internal factors impact on EC migration and polarity, loss- or gain-of-function (LOF or GOF) assays *in vitro* can be performed (Fig.1A) [12**].

Wound healing assay

The wound healing assay is a common tool used to study cell migration under different experimental conditions (Fig.1A). Briefly, a wound is created by scratching the surface of a monolayer of adherent ECs [13]. Then, axial polarity can be analyzed at different time points by live imaging or in fixed samples. During this assay, axial polarization first occurs in cells that are in direct contact with the free-edge, called leader cells, through re-orientation of the MTOC and the Golgi apparatus in the direction of migration [4, 14–16]. Follower cells that are more distant from the wound subsequently re-orient and follow the leaders through pulling forces in adherens junctions through CCM [14].

In this assay, cell migration and axial polarity can be analyzed at different time-points by live imaging or in fixed samples. EC migration trajectories, morphology, and velocity can be easily analysed computationally to complement polarity analysis [17].

Flow assay

ECs exposed to shear stress react by aligning and polarizing against the flow direction starting at around 10 dyn/cm² [18, 19]. Different systems are available to expose ECs to flow: orbital shakers, microfluidic devices, etc [20**, 21**]. Briefly, flow chambers seeded with adherent ECs are attached to a fluidic system [22*] that cyclically flows medium to the culture surface (Fig.1A). Laminar or turbulent/disturbed flow can be easily implemented to mimic physiological or pathological processes, such as atherosclerosis [23–25], respectively.

Micropatterning

Cell migration and polarity are highly dependent on components of the microenvironment like flow, chemokines or its physical properties. *In vivo* conditions can be recreated *in vitro* using 2D or 3D micropatterns by regulating physical and biochemical composition of the

environment. Several techniques exist to create the micropatterns such as lithography, bioprinting and photopolymerization [26–29].

Polarity assessment in vitro

In vitro, EC axial polarity can be investigated in any cell line, including HUVECs, HMVECs and primary brain ECs isolated from mice. Nuclei (DAPI or Erg) and Golgi (Golp4, Golgi-97 or GM130) or MTOC (pericentrin) are commonly used to visualize ECs polarity axis either by staining [7**, 18, 19, 30–33] or by using fluorescent reporters (essential for live-imaging) like H2b–mCherry or Hoechst for nuclei and CellLight Golgi-GFP for Golgi or GFP– α -tubulin for MTOC [22*, 34]. Determination of Golgi-nucleus pairs can be done automatically by minimizing the distance between all possible pairs.

In the different assays, EC axial polarity of each cell is defined as the angle between the nucleus-Golgi axis and the edge of the wounded monolayer or the flow direction using ImageJ, Oriana or MatLab (Fig.1C) [7**, 18, 19]. Angular histograms show angle distributions (Fig.1C) and polarity indexes (PIs) (Fig.1D) calculated based on the length of the mean resultant vector for a given angular distribution. The PI ranged from 0 to 1, where 0 corresponds to a random distribution and 1 corresponds to a perfect polarization towards a given direction (Fig.1D). These PI values can be used as a direct readout for CCM [7**, 18, 19, 30–33].

This type of analysis can also be performed in subsets of cells. For instance, leader cells, identified as the first row of cells directly in contact with the scratch, can be analysed in opposition to follower cells, comprising the subsequent rows of cells [7**].

Assays and methods to quantify endothelial cell axial polarity *in vivo*

In vivo models are essential to investigate EC axial polarization in response to flow and chemokines in a complex system. However, *in vivo* assessment of EC polarity is more challenging than *in vitro*. To do so, researchers have developed tools allowing the visualization of EC polarity *in vivo* in fixed tissues or by live imaging in mice and zebrafish (Fig.1B).

Mouse models

Different mouse models can be used to study polarity regarding flow or chemokines in fixed tissues (stainings or reporter lines) but also by live imaging (reporter lines) (Fig.1B).

One of the most common mouse models to study angiogenesis in fixed tissues is the retinal vascular network, which develops postnatally in a stereotypical manner, allowing the observation of the different stages of angiogenesis [35, 36]. Moreover, the planar structure of the retinal vascular network makes it easy to image at high-resolution [37]. 3D and 4D images can also be generated by using light-sheet fluorescence microscopy [38**]. Mouse coronary arteries [19] and dermal lymphatic vessels [39*] can also be used as models of fixed tissues to study ECs polarity as their network structure is well-known. An aortic denudation model was also developed to study the regeneration of the endothelial lining *in vivo* [40].

Live imaging of the vascular network of mice is more challenging due to the access issues and the need for reporter lines to assess polarity. Intravital imaging using multiphoton confocal microscopy through cranial windows [41] or in the ear are commonly used [42].

Polarity assessment

EC axial polarity can be visualized and assessed through stainings (fixed tissues) or by using fluorescent reporter mice (fixed tissues and live imaging). In fixed samples, tissues are stained for Golgi (Golp4 or GM130) and EC nuclei (ERG). As Golgi markers are not specific for ECs, polarity vectors from the nucleus to the Golgi of each EC must be assigned manually [7**, 8, 33]. As reporter mice, Barbacena et al. created a Cre recombinase-dependent inducible fluorescent reporter mouse line, labelling Golgi (mCherry) and nuclei (eGFP), to study axial polarity, the GNrep mouse line [43**]. Polarity analysis in this line can be performed both in fixed tissues or by intravital live-imaging. Polarity vectors can be assigned manually or in an automated way by using programs like Matlab [43**] (Fig.1C).

Once nucleus-to-Golgi vectors are assessed for each cell, EC axial polarity can be measured in relation to blood flow or chemokines. In fixed tissues, flow direction can be estimated using computational fluid dynamics. A free software tool is available, PolNet [44, 45]. In live imaging, flow direction can be assessed by injecting fluorescently labelled beads, high-

molecular weight dextrans into the vascular system, or by using fluorescently-labelled red blood cells. Tracking the movement of these particles in the vasculature provides a readout for blood flow velocity and direction [42]. Flow direction can be used as a reference to calculate EC axial polarity in response to haemodynamics, similarly to in vitro assays (Fig.1D). *In vivo*, there is a linear correlation between increasing wall shear stress and EC axial polarity [8].

Zebrafish models

The zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) embryo is a great animal model in cardiovascular research (Fig.1B). Its transparency, rapid development and easy genetic manipulations make it an optimal model to visualise cellular activities, such as cell migration, cellular rearrangements and cell divisions [46–48]. Several fluorescent transgenic lines have been generated to visualise EC dynamics and biological activities.

Polarity assessment

To study cell front–rear polarity in zebrafish, researchers have used transgenic lines, such as: Tg[fli1a:EGFP]^{y1}, Tg[fli1a:nEGFP]^{y7}, Tg[fli1a:dsRedEX]^{um13}, Tg[-0.8flt1:RFP]^{hu5333}, Tg[fli1a:B4GalT1-mCherry]^{bns9}, Tg(kdrl:NLS-EGFP)^{ubs10}, or Tg(fli1a:B4GALT1-mCherry) [8, 10, 11, 49**, 50*]. As previously described in other models, Golgi apparatus position relative to the nucleus has been used to define EC axial polarity [8]. EC polarization patterns can be defined as “upwards”, if the Golgi was located on the ahead of the nucleus, “unpolarised”, if the Golgi was located by the middle of the nucleus and “downwards”, if the Golgi was located on the behind the nucleus [11]. For quantitative analyses of EC polarization, it is necessary to manually determine EC axial polarity through the measurement of the angle between the nucleus–Golgi vector and a vector pointing toward the expected direction of migration (Fig.1C and D). This analysis is generally performed in the dorsal aorta, the posterior cardinal vein and intersegmental vessels [8, 49**], but other vascular beds are also suitable for analysis.

Conclusion

In this review, we highlighted recent *in vitro* and *in vivo* methods and animal models currently used to study EC axial polarity. Taking advantage of these methods, researchers have shown the relevance of EC axial polarity during CCM in sprouting angiogenesis, and in vascular patterning [7**, 18, 31, 33]. The molecular mechanisms regulating EC axial polarity are now being actively investigated. For instance, EC uses VE-cadherin-rich membrane protrusions, “cadherin fingers”, to regulate CCM [51]. Wnt5a, Cdc42, Nck1/2, Kif26a, Par3, and APJ have been shown to regulate EC axial polarity either in response to biochemical or mechanical cues in the context of vascular morphogenesis [7**, 11, 18, 30–33]. Recently, EC axial polarity and migration against the flow have been proved to be fundamental for arterialization of the vascular networks, in crosstalk with Notch and Cxcr4/Cxcl12 signalling [52–54].

Further refinement of animal models, imaging modalities, deep learning-based computational tools and statistical analyses will greatly impact our understanding of the role of EC axial polarity on vascular morphogenesis and vascular malformations.

Key points

1. EC axial polarization is regulated by blood flow and chemokines.
2. Nuclei and Golgi apparatuses can be used to visualise EC axial polarization.
3. Analysis of EC axial polarization has shed light on fundamental principles of angiogenesis.

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Conflict of interests

None

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Papers of particular interest, published within the annual period of review, have been highlighted as:

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Figure legend

Figure 1 - Models to quantify EC axial polarity.

(A) *In vitro* methods: wound assay - wound edge of migrating HUVEC monolayer; flow assay- HUVEC monolayer in a flow chamber. In both methods ECs were labelled in green for nuclei (DAPI), in red for Golgi (GM130) and in blue for actin (phalloidin).

(B) *In vivo* methods: GNrep mouse retina - ECs were labelled in green for nuclei (eGFP), in red for Golgi (mCherry) and in blue for EC apical membrane (ICAM2); representative image of the caudal plexus from a Tg([fli1a:nEGFP]^{y7}; [Fliep:mcherry-GM130]) zebrafish embryo. ECs were labelled in green for nuclei (GFP) and in red for Golgi (mCherry).

(C) EC axial polarity can be assessed upon a migration stimulus or after flow exposure. EC axial polarity is defined as: the angle (α) between the scratch edge and the cell polarity axis, defined by the vector drawn from the centre of the cell nucleus to the centre of the Golgi apparatus (axial polarity); or the angle (α) between the flow direction and the cell polarity axis, defined by the axial polarity vector. Representative angular histograms of the EC axial polarity assessed under ECs migration or flow.

(D) The polarity index (PI) is calculated and quantified according to the given formula. This index is used as a measure for the strength of collective polarization. PI varies between 0 (ECs have randomized) and 1 (ECs are strongly polarized). Representative graphs of the PI value for ECs under migration or flow conditions.

models to quantify endothelial cell axial polarity

